

THE CLASSIFICATION OF KARAKALPAK AND ENGLISH TOPONYMS

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Abstract. Toponym is the study of names of places, specifically their meanings, typology, use, and origins. The term toponym is derived from the Greek word *topos* meaning "region" and *onoma* meaning "to name." The study of regional names is called toponymy which is a branch of onomastics. Toponym also refers to a geographical entity or any general name for any place. Therefore, it is a good way to study toponyms by dividing them into categories which they belong to. As a result, the main focus of the research is to classify toponyms according to their principles in English and Karakalpak languages.

Keywords: toponyms, onomastics, classification, principles, English language, Karakalpak language.

Some linguists tried to classify toponyms combining different principles simultaneously. One of the first researchers to classify place names in any systematic manner was George R. Stewart. In 1954, he published an article in *Names* entitled "A classification of place names". His typology based on the "naming-process" recognizes ten main toponym types: [3].

- 1) descriptive names and compass-point names (names that describe and characterize the object's quality or its location;
- 2) associative names (names that evoke associations with different objects associated with a person, G. Stewart also refers to this group acts of God, calendar names, animal names, names of human actions, names from feelings, names from sayings);
- 4) possessive names (names originated from some idea of ownership);
- 5) commemorative names (names given in memory or in honor of outstanding people and names for abstract virtues);
- 6) commendatory names (names given by some attractive peculiarities of a geographical object);
- 7) folk etymologies (names with false etymology);
- 8) manufactured names (names which have been consciously constructed of fragments of other words, or names from initials, by reversals of letters or syllables, or in other ways);

9) mistake names (names appeared from a mistake made in the transmission from one language to another, either from inaccurate hearing of what was said, or because of faulty rendering of the sounds in writing);

10) shift names (names which have been moved from one location to another)

According to this classification, it is time to analyze the toponyms in English and Karakalpak languages. The following table shows the differences and similarities of toponyms in two languages: [4, 18-20].

English toponyms	Karakalpak toponyms
descriptive names and compass-point names	
Rocky Mountains, Chicago,	Qarataw, Shılpıq.
associative names	
Mill River (a mill was on the river), Springfield,	Ashshı kòl, Gùlbàhàr, Kòk òzek, Qoñırat, arshan, Badaytoǵay,
incident names	
Battle Creek, Bloody Ridge, Cut and Shoot,	Arıslan, Batır, Saratan, Jawza, Hùt, Hamal, Gùldirsın, Quwanışbay
possessive names	
Castro Valley, Pittsburgh,	Aqtuba, Aqterek, Taqıyatas.
Commemorative names	
St Louis, San Jacinto, Houston, Seattle (named after Chief Seattle),	Shomanay, Temurbekler mektebi, Beruniy rayonı, Sultan Ways,

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Austin, Pennsylvania (Penn's Woods), Illinois (after the Illini Indians),	Marokanda, Xòjeli,
commendatory names	
Pleasant Valley, Greenland,	Nurata, Ùshjapsağa, Adaykòl
folk etymologies	
the toponym of Hellespont was explained by Greek poets as being named after Helle, daughter of Athamas, who drowned here as she crossed it with her brother Phrixus on a flying golden ram. The name, however, most likely is derived from an older language, such as Pelasgian, and probably meant "good port".	Qanlıkòl, Ayazqala, Gùldirsin
manufactured names	
Tesnus (Sunset spelled backwards), Reklaw (Walker spelled backwards) Iraan (Ira and Ann name the town after each other),	
mistake names	
West Indies (not west of the Indies and not the Indies),	Burlaq, Tañatar, Ùshsay,
shift names	
Athens (Greece and Texas), Palestine (Middle East and Texas), New Mexico (settlers from Mexico named their new home after their previous home), New England	Chambil, Urganji, Diyxanabat

The presented classification of toponyms in English and Karakalpak languages depicted that there are similarities and differences of toponyms in both

languages. It is obvious from the table that there is no manufactured names in Karakalpak language.

Conclusion. Taking all into account, it is clear that the study of toponyms is important in linguistics as it shows the uniqueness of place names. The presented classification of toponyms in English and Karakalpak languages depicted that there are similarities and differences of toponyms in both languages. It is obvious from the research that there is no manufactured names in Karakalpak language.

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